

Spectrophotometric Study of the Complexation Reaction between Yttrium (III) and Hematoxylin (Oxidised)

SUNIL P. PANDE & KAILASH N. MUNSHI

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur

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The formation of violet coloured chelate of yttrium (III) with Hematoxylin (oxidised) has been described. Composition and stability constant for the chelate was studied by different methods at four different fixed values of ionic strength. The chelate has composition 1 : 2 (metal : reagent) with a λ_{\max} of 560 nm at pH 6.5. Thermodynamic stability constant of the chelate has been found out to be 9.6 ± 0.2 . The study also includes the analytical applications of the metal chelate.

The property of Hematoxylin (oxidised) to form coloured complexes with metal ions has been utilised by many workers¹⁻⁵. Sarma and Raghava Rao⁶ have reported hematoxylin (oxidised) as a colorimetric reagent for lanthanum and yttrium and also the composition of the complex. The present communication describes the detailed study of the complexation reaction of yttrium (III) with oxidised hematoxylin (abbreviated as HTX) and reports the complex formation, composition of the complex formed, values of log K calculated at different fixed values of ionic strength, thermodynamic stability constant, and other analytical characteristics of this system.

EXPERIMENTAL

Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Beckman model DU-2 spectrophotometer, using glass cells of 1 cm. path length. For pH measurements, Beckman direct reading H-2 model pH-meter with glass calomel electrode system was used. The solution of Y(III) was prepared by dissolving its chloride (E. Merck) in distilled water, acidified and estimated as usual⁷. All other solutions were prepared by using reagents of analytical grade. Solution of HTX (B.D.H.) was prepared in water alcohol mixture and was then oxidised by H_2O_2 .¹

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of pH on the Reagent : The variation in λ_{\max} with change in pH of reagent alone was studied by taking $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ solution. It was found that the reagent solution has a λ_{\max} 430 nm from pH 1.0 to 7.0, 550 nm from pH 7.5 to 8.5, and 480 nm from pH 9.0 to 10.0. After pH 10.0 the colour of the reagent fades away rapidly.

Absorption Spectra and Composition of the Chelates formed : The study of absorption spectra shows the existence of only one complex having a λ_{\max} of 560 nm in the pH range of 6.5 to 7.5. However, pH 6.5 was selected for study, as the λ_{\max} of the reagent is only

430 nm at this pH , and also to avoid the hydrolysis of the metal ion. The composition of $Y(III)$ -HTX chelate was studied by different methods indicating the composition, of the chelate as 1 : 2 (metal : reagent), at pH 6.5 and at 560 nm, as reported earlier⁶.

Calculation of the stability constant : The value of $\log K$ of the chelate was calculated by three different methods: (a) method of Foley and Anderson⁸, modified by Mukherji and Dey⁹, (b) mole ratio method¹⁰ and (c) limiting logarithmic method¹¹. The experiments were performed at four different fixed values of ionic strength (μ) maintained by the addition of suitable quantity of sodium perchlorate solution. The values of $\log K$ obtained by different methods are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1
Values of $\log K$ of $Y(III)$ -HTX (1 : 2) Chelate at 27°

Method	Ionic Strength (μ)			
	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20
(a)	8.8 \pm 0.2	8.7 \pm 0.2	8.4 \pm 0.2	8.0 \pm 0.2
(b)	9.4 \pm 0.2	9.35 \pm 0.2	9.3 \pm 0.2	9.25 \pm 0.2
(c)	9.5 \pm 0.2	9.2 \pm 0.2	9.1 \pm 0.2	8.8 \pm 0.2

Thermodynamic stability constant of the chelate was determined by plotting a graph of average value of $\log K$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ and extrapolating it to zero ionic strength. The value so obtained is = 9.6 \pm 0.2.

Position of Chelate ring : The oxidation of hematoxylin by H_2O_2 produces hematein which has the following structure :

In this structure there are two possible positions for chelation : (i) through two adjacent phenolic oxygens and (ii) through quinoid oxygen and adjacent phenolic group. Electrophoresis experiments and absorption of colour of the chelate by a resin Amberlite IR 45(OH) show that the chelate is anionic in nature and on the basis of this study, position (i) of chelation seems to be more probable.

Analytical studies of the chelate : The colour formation of the chelate is instantaneous. However, the colour is stable only upto 8 hrs, and starts fading slowly thereafter. Hence for experiments with HTX all reagent solutions were freshly prepared and absorbance of the mixtures were noted within 8 hr of the preparation of the mixture. The colour intensity of the complex is stable in the temperature range of 25° to 70°. At least five fold excess of reagent is necessary to have the maximum colour formation. The system adhered to Beer's law in the concentration range of 0.71–1.78 ppm of yttrium, at pH 6.5 and 560 nm. The sensitivity of the colour reaction was found to be 0.11 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (practical) and 0.011 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (Sandell). The value of molar extinction coefficient was calculated to be = 10,830 at pH 6.5 and at 560 nm.

The effect of various anions and cations on the system was studied spectrophotometrically and it was observed that the reagent is not selective due to large number of interfering ions. But on the basis of the value of molar extinction coefficient it can be treated as a sensitive reagent for the determination of yttrium (III) in aqueous solution.

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